

IMPACT DAMAGE GROWTH AND FAILURE OF CARBON-FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC SKIN-STRINGER PANELS

Emile Greenhalgh, Sunil Singh, Donald Roberts

Structural Materials Centre, DRA, Farnborough, Hants, UK, GU14 6TD

SUMMARY: This paper describes an investigation into low velocity impact damage in skin-stringer panels. The effect of panel geometry and impact site on the damage growth and compressive strength was investigated. Impact damage beneath a stringer was less detrimental to strength than damage in the bay. In five of the six panels, failure was precipitated by a combination of bay buckling and skin/stringer detachment, except in one panel where massive lateral delamination growth led to a large reduction in strength. For impact damage in a bay, a wide-bay/thick-skin design was the most damage tolerant whilst for impact damage beneath a stringer, a high buckling strain design was the most tolerant. The results suggest that, at current in-service strain levels, impact damage may be tolerated in some cases.

KEYWORDS: structures, impact, fractography, delamination, skin-stringer, buckling

INTRODUCTION

The specific in-plane properties of carbon-fibre composites make them invaluable for use in aircraft structures. However, they are limited by their inherent susceptibility to impact and other out-of-plane loadings. In coupons a low velocity impact can reduce the compressive properties by up to 50% [1]. However, damage in coupons is more severe than that in structures since, in the latter, much of the incident energy is absorbed through elastic structural response [2]. Only through tests on structural elements (skin-stringer panels) can the damage processes and failure of impacted composite structures be understood.

There has only been limited work conducted on the effect of impact damage on skin-stringer panels. Madan showed that the greatest strength reduction was from bay impacts [3]. However, most studies have investigated 'softer' skinned panels; *i.e.* containing few 0° plies [4,5]. In these structures, impact over the stringers led to the greatest reductions in strength.

This paper describes the second part of an investigation into impact damage in skin-stringer panels. In the first part of the work panels of different geometries were impacted at 15J at various sites [2]. For impacts over the panel bay, the energy was mainly absorbed through the formation of delaminations and matrix cracking. However, as the impact site approached the stringer, or the bay aspect ratio increased, more energy was absorbed through elastic response, leading to less severe damage states. Generally, the damage distribution through the thickness was conical. In the bays, it was roughly circular in area whilst over the stringer feet it was elliptical, with the major axis parallel to the stringers. The damage from impact over the stringer centreline was negligible.

In this part of the investigation identical panels were impacted either over the bay or the stringer foot, and then tested to failure in quasi-static compression. The effect of panel geometry and impact location were addressed, and compared with results from similar panel tests with embedded defects [6].

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The stiffened carbon-fibre reinforced panels (Figure 1), each made up of a quasi-isotropic skin ($[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{nS}$) and three I-section stringers, were manufactured. Seven panels, of three different geometries were studied. The first (Type 1) was designed to buckle at a compressive strain of $6000\mu\epsilon$ whilst the second and third panels were designed to buckle at $3700\mu\epsilon$. In the second case (Type 2) this was achieved by increasing the stringer spacing and in the third case (Type 3) by decreasing the skin-thickness. One panel of each type was compressively tested with impact damage either in the bay or in the stringer foot regions. Further details of the manufacture and preparation of the panels are given elsewhere [2].

Figure 1: Geometries and impact sites in the skin-stringer panels

The panels were impacted using instrumented drop-weight equipment at an incident energy of 15J; all the impacts were applied to the skin on the outer (non-stringer) face. The panels were impacted at the mid-length, 150mm from the panel ends, either in the left bay, or over the tapered section of the central stringer foot. The seventh panel was subjected to a 30J impact at the mid-length over the centreline of the left-hand stringer foot. The panel was of the Type 1 design and had originally been used to study the effect of artificial defects on the performance of skin-stringer panels [6], but did not fail during testing.

After impacting, the dent depth and damage area (ultrasonic attenuation of 6dB or more compared with best material) were measured. The panels were then compressively tested at a rate of 0.005mm/s and the strains, displacements and loads recorded. Displacement transducers and Moiré interferometry were used to monitor out-of-plane deformations of the damaged regions and the stringer deflections. Following testing to failure, the panels were photographed, and examined to determine the damage growth and failure processes [7].

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

When compared to the previous studies [2], the impact forces, deflections and damage areas were found to be repeatable, particularly for impacts over the stringer feet. For identical impacts, the damage was generally similar in shape and distribution through the thickness. However, for impacts over the bay, the damage areas differed by as much as 26%.

Table 1: Results from the compressive tests on the skin-stringer panels

Panel Type	Type 1			Type 2		Type 3	
Impact Location	Bay	Foot	Centreline	Bay	Foot	Bay	Foot
Damage Area (mm²)	2141	778	50	675	824	534	1071
Buckling Strain (μϵ)	-	-5803	-7100	-4400	-4500	-3530	-4600
Failure Strain (μϵ)	-3662	-5803	-7464	-4543	-4964	-3597	-4697
Failure Load (kN)	-529	-803	-995	-734	-840	-460	-554

The results of the compressive testing of the skin-stringer panels are shown in Table 1. In general, damage in the bay was more critical than damage beneath the stringer foot, particularly for the Type 1 panel. Impact damage beneath the stringer centreline had a negligible effect on the panel strength and did not initiate failure of the structure.

Figure 2 shows the typical damage development from an impact in the bay.

Figure 2: Development of the damage in a Type 3 panel with a bay impact

The image width is equivalent to the bay width and each Moiré fringe is equivalent to an out-of-plane deflection change of 0.2mm. The applied strain is shown below each image.

For the panels with impacts in the bay the early damage development was similar for all three types. Upon loading the impacted region formed a blister and the bay displaced outwards, away from the stringers. The blister was elliptical, with the major axis perpendicular to the applied load, and was highest in the Type 3 panel. However, the blister was smaller than the damage observed from the non-destructive analysis. The damage grew laterally in a stable manner from the impact site across the bay width. In the panels with 120mm bay widths, at an applied strain of about $-3500\mu\epsilon$ the growth became more rapid, extending towards and beneath the stringers. However, in the panel with a 148mm wide bay, the damage growth was limited, and the damage front did not reach the stringers before panel buckling.

The Type 1 panel failed at a strain well below the design strain ($-3662\mu\epsilon$). The Type 2 and 3 panels failed at and beyond buckling, at strains of $-4543\mu\epsilon$ and $-3597\mu\epsilon$ respectively. The Type 2 panel exhibited significant post-buckling performance and the buckling strain was only slightly depressed. However, the Type 3 panel exhibited a significant fall in buckling strain, and failed during panel buckling.

The performance of the panels containing impact damage beneath the stringer foot were very different to those containing damage in the bays. As the load was applied the damaged region started to displace outwards, with the largest displacement in the bay adjacent to the impact site. There was little damage growth observed although there was some lifting of the stringer foot from the skin. The Type 1 panel failed as it buckled at a strain of $-5803\mu\epsilon$ whilst the Type 2 and 3 panels both buckled at values greater than their design strains. The Type 3 panel failed soon after buckling ($-4697\mu\epsilon$) and the Type 2 panel had significant post-buckling performance, failing at a strain of $-4964\mu\epsilon$.

Failure analysis (fractography) showed that five out of the six panels which had failed due to impact damage, had failed in a similar manner. After the initial growth stages, the combination of damage beneath the stringer foot and bay buckling precipitated detachment of the stringer from the skin. This led to skin crippling and catastrophic panel failure. In the Type 1 panel with damage in the bay, massive unstable delamination spread across the panel width, leading to catastrophic failure of the skin.

DISCUSSION

Damage Growth and Failure Mechanisms

Before discussing the effect of various parameters, the mechanisms for damage growth and structural failure should be considered. The overriding factor in controlling these mechanisms was the location of the impact site; the failure processes of the panels with impact damage in the bay was very different to that of the panels with damage beneath the stringer feet. An impact over the stringer centreline had a negligible effect on the panel failure.

The failure processes for a panel containing impact damage in the bay is shown in Figure 3. As the load was introduced the impacted bay deflected outwards, away from the stringer face (Figure 3a). The damaged region also started to deflect, but inwards, towards the stringer face (Figure 3b) and the damage started to grow from the impact site (Figure 3c). The damage growth was predominantly transverse, growing towards the stringers. Initially the growth was stable, but there reached a point where it became unstable and rapidly spreading across the bay and beneath the stringers.

Figure 3: Failure mechanisms for panels with an impacted bay

The later stages of damage growth were dependant on the panel type. In the panel designed to the higher buckling strain (Type 1) the damage continued to spread across the panel width (Figure 3d), rapidly developing into the undamaged bay and beneath all the stringers. Once the damage had spread over 80% of the panel width, compressive failure of the remaining skin initiated in the impacted bay and spread across the entire panel width (Figure 3e).

In the panels designed to the lower buckling strain (Types 2 and 3), the failure mechanism was different. As the damage grew towards the stringers, the bays started to buckle. As in the panels containing single plane defects in the bay [6] the presence of the damage reduced the panel buckling strain. As the bays buckled, opening forces were promoted beneath the stringers, leading to local detachment of the stringers from the skin (Figure 3f). This loss of local support led to skin instability (cripling) and compressive failure (initiating at the impact site), and finally the stringers detached and failed in flexure (Figure 3g).

All three panels which were impacted over the stringer foot failed by the same damage process (Figure 4). Although the early stages of damage growth were different to those observed in the panels containing impacts in the bay, the later stages of growth and failure were similar to those observed in the Type 2 and 3 panels. Firstly, as the load was introduced, the bay adjacent to the impacted stringer started to deflect outwards (Figure 4a), eventually

leading to lifting of the stringer foot. There was no transverse damage growth, but damage spread longitudinally, along the stringer foot (Figure 4b). The rate of damage growth was much less than that observed in the panels containing damage in the bay, leading to higher strains to failure. Eventually, the panels buckled which promoted partial stringer detachment (Figure 4c). As with the impacts in the bay, this led to skin crippling, compressive failure (initiating from the impact site) and failure of the central stringer (Figure 4d).

Figure 4: Failure mechanism for panels with an impacted stringer foot

The failure of the panel containing the impact damage on the stringer centreline was not attributed to the impact damage. The failure initiated as massive lateral delamination growth across most of the panel width, initiating from the artificial defect. This was followed by stringer detachment and compressive failure of the skin.

Effect of Impact Location

As shown in Figure 5, the impact location had the largest effect on the panel performance.

Firstly, consider the Type 1 design of which there were three panels tested. Since the failure of the panel containing the damage beneath the stringer centreline was not due to the impact, this can be treated as a lower bound on the undamaged strength of this design. Considering this, a 15J impact over the stringer foot led to a 12% drop in strength whilst a similar impact in the bay led to a 51% drop in strength, the latter representing a significant drop in strength.

For the other two panel types the undamaged strengths were not known. However, there was less reduction in strength between the stringer feet and bay impacts (9% and 23% for the Type 2 and 3 panels respectively) than was observed in the Type 1 panel (37%). The reduction in the Type 3 panels was attributed to the bay damage reducing the buckling strain which promoted stringer detachment. In the Type 2 panels, the failure mechanisms due to damage in the bay and stringer foot were very similar, leading to the negligible drop in strength.

Figure 5: Failure strains for skin-stringer panels containing impact damage

Effect of Panel Geometry

For impact to the bay, there was a clear effect of panel type on the failure process. The Type 1 panel did not buckle and failed due to massive delamination growth. The Type 2 panel exhibited little damage growth and failed by a combination of bay buckling and stringer detachment. In the Type 3 panel, the failure was attributed to stringer detachment which was promoted by the reduced buckling performance of the damaged bay. The higher failure strain in the Type 2 panel was due to the slower development of the damage. This was attributed to the impact damage being distant from the stringer feet and the out-of-plane deflection of the damaged region being less than that in the other panel types. This subsequently led to two factors which improved the damage tolerance for this design. Firstly, the reduced growth led to the damage having less of an influence on buckling. Secondly, the damage had less effect on the stringers, not promoting stringer detachment to the same extent in the Type 3 design.

For the damage beneath the stringer feet, there was less effect of panel geometry. Firstly, the damage had little effect on buckling, therefore not promoting failure to the same extent as from bay damage. The largest effect of geometry was observed in the Type 3 panels, again due to the sensitivity of this design to stringer debonding.

Comparison with Embedded Defects

In earlier work [6], Type 1 panels containing Teflon discs between the plies were tested. These defects were located at either of two different ply interfaces and were either in the bay or beneath the stringer foot. The results were compared to the current work to gauge the validity of modelling impact as single plane defects. There were some similarities between the growth processes for the two types of damage. In both instances the damaged bay firstly deflected outwards and the initial growth was transverse to the loading direction, leading to the damage extending towards the stringer feet. However, at a given applied strain, the height and width of the impact damage were much less than those of the artificial damage. This was attributed to the impact damage consisting of small, deep defects which could not deflect outward to the same extent that the relatively large, shallow single-plane defects could.

As the damage front approached the stringer feet, the growth processes were accelerated. In the panel containing impact damage in the bay this led to catastrophic compressive failure. However, in the panels containing artificial defects, the growth promoted stringer detachment only after panel buckling. For similar damage areas, the impacted panel had 60% of the strength of the panel containing an artificial defect. In the panels containing artificial defects, the growth was dominated by blistering of the surface plies and was subsequently dominated by stable mode I growth [8,9]. In the impacted panel the damage was mainly deeper and mode II dominated, so stable damage growth was limited. Furthermore, the local bending of the damaged region subsequently led to unstable mode II growth from the impact site. When the damage was beneath the stringers, the out-of-plane constraint on the skin inhibited mode I dominated growth, as from the artificial damage, but would have had little effect on mode II dominated growth, as from the impact damage. For both impact damage and artificial defects beneath the stringer, the strength reduction was less than that from those in the bay.

IMPLICATIONS IN-SERVICE AND FOR DESIGN

The current results allow some prediction of the severity of the damage and suggest that in many cases an impact over the stringer can be tolerated. Furthermore, damage beneath the stringer had little effect on panel buckling and only for designs sensitive to skin/stringer debonding did damage beneath the stringer become significant. When impact damage was present in the bays, rapid unstable growth, sometimes leading directly to failure, occurred at strains above $-3500\mu\epsilon$ (below most aircraft limit loads).

Based on studies from material testing, the current philosophy is to gauge the severity of an impact by the damage area; the larger the damage area, the lower the failure strain, and this relationship did hold for stringer foot impacts. However, for impacts to the bay, large damage areas did not necessarily correspond to low failure strains since the panel geometry had a significant effect on the failure processes.

Understanding of the damage growth and failure processes can be utilised to produce impact tolerance in new structural designs. The driving force for impact damage growth was a combination of mode II forces generated by bending of the damaged region, and mode I forces from the blistering of the surface plies. However, unlike embedded defects, relatively little stable damage growth was observed prior to panel buckling. The wide-bay/thick-skin design exhibited the slowest damage development before failure and consequently had the highest strength.

A measure with which to rank the damage tolerance is the load intensity/unit areal weight [6] as shown in Figure 6.

All these panel designs were less tolerant of damage within the bay than beneath the stringer foot, particularly for the high buckling strain structures (Type 1). Impacts over the stringer foot did not pose a significant threat whilst those over the stringer centreline had no observed effect on strength. It should be noted that all these designs had relatively 'hard' skins; a significant proportion of the load was carried by the skin. In 'soft' skin designs (most of the load is carried by the stringers) impact damage beneath the stringers may be more critical.

For the low buckling strain designs, the wide-bay/thick-skin approach (Type 2) was clearly the more damage tolerant, particularly for impacts to the bay. Comparing all three panel types,

for bay impacts this design (Type 2) also out-performed the high strain buckling design (Type 1). However, for stringer foot impacts, where the panel buckling precipitated failure in all panel types, the high buckling strain design was the most damage tolerant.

Figure 6: Load intensity/unit areal weight for skin-stringer panels

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions have been drawn from investigations of the damage, growth and structural failure in damaged skin-stringer panels under compressive loading:

1. Generally, the forces, displacements and damage areas were reproducible, except that the damage areas from impacts over the bay which exhibited a large degree of scatter.
2. There was no direct relationship between impact damage area and failure strain.
3. In panels containing impact damage in the bays, the damage firstly spread laterally towards the stringers, which in some cases significantly reduced the panel buckling strain. During buckling, this led to stringer detachment, skin crippling and catastrophic failure. In the high buckling strain design, massive unstable delamination growth occurred, promoting failure.
4. In panels containing impact damage beneath the stringer foot, the local substructure constrained and limited damage growth. Failure eventually occurred when the panel buckled; the combination of the out-of-plane deflection of the bay and the presence of damage beneath the stringer led to stringer detachment and catastrophic failure.
5. Panels containing impact damage in the bay exhibited a strength reduction of up to 37% with respect to panels containing impact damage beneath the stringer foot. Impact damage directly beneath the stringer centreline had a negligible effect on panel strength.
6. For the low buckling strain designs, a wide-bay/thick-skin was the most damage tolerant. Of all the panels tested, this design was the most tolerant to impacts in the bay whilst the high buckling strain design was the most tolerant of impact damage beneath the stringer foot.
7. Panels containing single plane embedded delaminations were 60% stronger than panels containing impact damage of the same dimensions.
8. At current in-service strain levels, impact damage may be tolerated in some cases. Certainly for low buckling strain designs, there was no significant reduction in strength. At current design strains for primary structures, damage may be tolerated in many cases.

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